

Local Government in Albania

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Albania	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Albania: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Decentralized Early Childhood Education</i>	9
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Albania: An Introduction.....	16
3.2. <i>The Allocation of the General-Purpose Unconditional Grant and Fiscal Equalization</i>	19
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Albania: An Introduction	26
4.2. <i>The Territorial and Administrative Reform</i>	29
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Albania: An Introduction.....	36
5.2. <i>Intergovernmental Dialogue through a Formal Two-Level Executive Mechanism of Policy Consultation and Coordination: CLFCC</i>	38
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Albania: An Introduction	44
6.2. <i>Atelier Kanina - 100 Albanian Villages: Civic Engagement Towards Urban-Rural Linkages</i>	48

Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Albania: An Introduction

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Intergovernmental relations refer to all the processes, mechanisms and institutions in place in a given country through which the various levels of government interact and relate with one another to exercise government power and achieve common or concurrent policy purposes.²⁶ The nature and intensity of intergovernmental relations may differ substantially from country to country depending on the form of the political and legal system, levels of government, territorial and administrative division, socio-economic development, history and tradition, political climate, legal framework etc. Intergovernmental relations in Albania are characterized by both formal as well as informal structures, institutions and processes that build on mechanisms of both supervision and cooperation. As a general rule, Albania's Constitution provides the basic architecture of intergovernmental relations between the various levels of government, while more detailed relations are regulated by law and/or informal practices of exchange and cooperation. A key role in intergovernmental relations, is dedicated to the Associations of Local Authorities in Albania and more recently to the Agency for the Support of Local Self-Government and the Consultative Council between the Central and Local Governments. Similarly, also line ministries and local governments directly play a key role in the regulation and implementation of specific sectoral policies that cross-cut with local government responsibilities.

Within such formal and informal architecture, the different political and economic powers of urban and rural local self-governments may result in a different impact on intergovernmental relations. In fact, larger and more urban local governments are more actively represented in intergovernmental relations. In addition, the proximity of the institutions of Capital City of Tirana with the institutions of the central government, plays a key role in the fact that Tirana is represented in most of the intergovernmental working groups for sectoral policy reforms, as opposed to smaller and more rural local governments. To some extent this is explained also by the different capacities. This is particularly true in the design and revision of intergovernmental fiscal and financial systems that should take into consideration the needs of both urban and rural subnational governments. Furthermore, the political landscape and personalities involved in the key formal institutions definitively play a role in the effectiveness of both formal and informal channels of interaction, even when there is a long-standing and well-established tradition of interaction.

With decentralization processes going on for decades in Albania, local self-governments have become responsible for many public responsibilities which were previously considered an

²⁶ John Philimore, 'Understanding Intergovernmental Relations: Key Features and Trends' (2013) 72 *Australian Journal of Public Administration* 228.

exclusive competence of national governments. This has necessitated a revision of intergovernmental relations and accountabilities. Socio-demographic changes and the movement of citizens from rural to urban areas impose severe pressures on the relationships, responsibilities and capacities of urban and rural local self-government to deliver public services, necessitating a recurrent revision of intergovernmental fiscal relations.

Local Government Associations (LGAs) in Albania have a key role in the intergovernmental relations as they could contribute to consensus building and cooperation, while representing the interests of both urban and rural areas of the newly consolidated local governments. However, the role and impact of LGAs, in addition to tradition and legal statuses is greatly affected by their financial stability; internal democracy in decision-making to effectively represent the potential urban-rural divide and interplay; political climate and polarization; territorial and administrative divisions and reforms; etc.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 139/2015 on Local Self-Government

Decision of the Council of Ministers no 910/2016 on the Organization and Functioning of the Consultative Council between the Central Government and Local Self-Governments

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Philimore J, 'Understanding Intergovernmental Relations: Key Features and Trends' (2013) 72 Australian Journal of Public Administration 228

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